

EFFECT OF MILLING PARAMETERS ON CHIP CHARACTERISTICS OF A (MG-ZN-RE) MAGNESIUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

The Magnesium (Mg) alloys containing rare earths (RE), have gained prominence due to their low density and high specific strength. However, the effects of machining parameters on chip formation are not fully understood. In this context, this study aims to investigate the influence of milling conditions (milling mode, edge radius, feed rate, and depth of cut) of the (Mg-Zn-RE) Mg alloy on the characteristics of the chips, with regard to morphology, thickness, microstructure, and hardness. Sixteen cutting conditions were evaluated, combining two milling modes, two edge radius (r_β) levels, two feed rate (f) levels, and two depth of cut (a_p) levels. The analysis involved the use of characterization techniques such as optical microscopy (OM) and Vickers microhardness (HV). Results indicate that conditions with $a_p = 2$ mm generate arc-shaped chips, and $a_p = 1$ mm tend to be comma-shaped, while discordant conditions significantly influence chip fragmentation. Higher f (0.8 mm/rev) and up-milling increase chip thickness. Microstructural analysis shows increased precipitate density and plastic deformation, reflecting work hardening. Although microhardness was not significantly altered by the cutting parameters, conditions under discordant cutting and a smaller f (0.01 mm) produced harder chips, and in comparison, with the material "as received," there was a significant increase in the microhardness of the chips.

KEYWORDS: Milling, Mg alloys, Chip, Cutting parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for materials that are lightweight, durable, and easy to machine is stimulating interest in magnesium (Mg) alloys in various industries, such as automotive, aerospace, and biomedical. Due to their low density, high strength-to-weight ratio, good machinability, and high thermal conductivity, these materials represent a promising alternative to address the need for replacing traditional alloys in structural and functional component applications. Its main advantages in machining are: long tool life, reduced processing time due to their low density, low energy consumption, about 55% less than for aluminum alloys, short chips, and good surface finish [1].

Recently, there has been growing interest in research analyzing the feasibility of reusing chips generated during machining, not only considering them as metal waste, but as inputs for secondary processes. In this context, Castro et al. [2], developed a magnesium (MgAl_2O_3) composite by consolidating pure Mg machining chips with 10% by volume of alumina particles through high-pressure torsion, proving that the chips can be reused in the manufacture of materials with improved microstructural structure, hardness, and creep resistance compared to the original product.

Similarly, Hao et al. [3], noticed that direct casting of Mg alloy (AZ91/AZ80) machining chips improved grain refinement during the solidification process, and the tensile properties of the castings were preserved, compared to casting ingots of the same alloy. In addition, Lakshminarayanan et al. [4], point out that the reuse of Mg alloy chips (ZE41) through the friction extrusion process leads to the formation of highly refined microstructures, with a reduction in grain size from 100 μm to 18 μm , and an increase of up to 40% in hardness compared to the original alloy, as a result of the creation of ultrafine grains and the reduction of internal heterogeneities.

In addition, the use of Mg-Ni chips from machining processes represents an efficient way to store hydrogen. As demonstrated by Aminorroaya et al. [5], high-energy ball milling of a mixture of Mg alloy chips (Mg-6% Ni) with 5 wt% MWCNTs yielded a powder with a refined microstructure. This process ensures a homogeneous dispersion of the MWCNTs, which expands the material's active surface area and creates efficient pathways for hydrogen diffusion. The result was rapid absorption of H_2 , reaching maximum storage capacity in just a few minutes, along with improved kinetics for both absorption and desorption.

Among machining techniques, milling has been extensively used in the manufacture of Mg alloy components, resulting in chips with distinct characteristics according to the cutting parameters employed. As demonstrated by Gobivel and Sekar [5], variables such as cutting speed ($v_c = 25, 50,$ and 75 m/min), feed rate ($f = 0.19, 0.22,$ and 0.25 mm/rev), and constant cutting depth ($a_p = 0.3$ mm) directly influenced the shape of the chips and machining forces during the milling of Mg alloy (AZ31B), providing crucial information about the mechanical material's performance characteristics throughout the process.

Complementing this analysis of machining conditions and their influence on magnesium alloy chips, Pawanr and Gupta [6], investigated the dry machining of AZ31B Mg alloy using textured cutting tools. They observed that cutting speed was the most significant factor in chip formation: at low cutting speeds ($v_c = 65$ m/min), the chips were discontinuous, while at higher speeds ($v_c = 90$ and 115 m/min), they became continuous and tangled. The study also demonstrated that texturing the tool surface with micro-dimps reduces contact area and heat generation, minimizing the risk of chip ignition and contributing to a safer and more sustainable machining operation.

Among the different classes of Mg alloys, those containing rare earth (RE) elements offer greater thermal stability and mechanical strength. However, most studies related to the machining of such alloys are of unconventional processes. A good example of this is the work of Parsana et al. [7], who developed a mathematical model for optimizing the parameters of electrical discharge machining (EDM) of a Mg alloy with rare earths (Mg-Zn-RE-Zr). The central focus of the study was to develop a relationship between the main process parameters and the responses of material removal rate (MRR), tool wear rate (TWR), and the morphology of the machined hole. Despite its importance, this investigation does not offer aspects directly related to chip formation and analysis, which reinforces the lack of research focused on conventional machining of this alloy.

Compared to other Mg alloys with rare earth elements (RE), the EZ33 alloy stands out for its refined microstructure and thermal stability, and good mechanical strength, and is widely used in aerospace structural components that require lightness and high-temperature performance. As highlighted by Rogal et al. [8], the EZ33 alloy, which is composed of Mg-Zn-RE-Zr, exhibits a microstructure with globular grains and intermetallic phases, and exhibits excellent mechanical properties after heat treatment, making it a promising option for technological applications that go beyond simple reuse as metal waste and that pay attention to the internal and external characteristics of chips, such as those mentioned above (hydrogen storage and metal matrix composites), but which have yet to be thoroughly investigated in the context of machining.

In this sense, considering the demand for more research related to chips generated by the machining of Mg alloys with rare earths, this study aims to analyze the influence of milling mode, edge radius (r_β), feed rate (f), and depth of cut (a_p) on the morphological, microstructural, and hardness properties of chips formed during face milling of a (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy similar to EZ33; in addition to the introduction, the materials and methods will be presented in section 2, the results and discussion will be presented in section 3, and finally, the conclusions will be presented in section 4.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure 1 shows a flowchart illustrating the methodology used in this study, in which, briefly, the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy was processed by end milling with sixteen (16) different cutting conditions, with the respective chips subjected to: optical microscopy (OM) to obtain a qualitative assessment of chips, complemented by thickness measurements and an evaluation of the microstructure; and Vickers microhardness (HV) for measuring the microhardness of the chips. The entire experimental procedure will be detailed in the following sections.

Figure 1. Structure of the methodology used, (MO) optical microscopy, (HV) Vickers microhardness.

2.1 Workpiece material

The magnesium (Mg) alloy used in this research has a composition similar to ASTM B80 EZ33 alloy [3%p Zn – 3%p mischmetal (RE – rare earths) - 1%p Zr], except for the absence of the element zirconium (Zr) in its chemical composition, thus becoming an alloy “Mg-Zn-RE system” [3%p Zn – 3%p mischmetal (RE – rare earths)], and therefore not yet catalogued. This alloy was acquired in cast condition with dimensions of 50 mm in length, 15 mm in thickness, and 10 mm in width after the work conducted by Barros Neto [9], in which the author analyzed the effects of Equal Channel Angular Pressing (ECAP) parameters on the microstructural evolution, mechanical behavior, and hydrogenation capacity (hydrogen absorption and desorption) in commercially pure Mg and its Mg alloy EZ33, for applications such as storage of H₂ by absorption (metal hydrides).

The mischmetal present in the alloy contains different proportions of rare earth elements (RE), including cerium (Ce), lanthanum (La), neodymium (Nd), and praseodymium (Pr), which are generally used to promote grain refinement, precipitates formation, and varied microstructural networks [10]. The chemical composition of the alloy studied in this work is shown in Table 1, evaluated with the aid of an Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer from Shimadzu, model EDX-720.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the (Mg-Zn-RE) Mg alloy studied in this work [9].

	Composition (%)					Mg
	Zn	Comp. Mischmetal (%)			Nd	
		La	Ce	Pr		
Mg alloy (Mg-Zn-RE)	3.602	0.873	1.45	0.407	1.044	balance

2.2 Milling tests

Milling trials were conducted on a VEKER/FIRST VKF 430i milling machine with 3.73 kW nominal power. The cutting tools used were two solid carbide end mills EC-H4M 10-20C10CF-E72 (ISO Class P10) from ISCAR, with 10 mm diameter, 38° helix angle, four edges, AlTiN coating, and cutting-edge radius values of 0.01 mm (10 μm) and 0.03 mm (30 μm). Figure 2 shows the machine tool configuration, and the chip's regions of interest for analysis (side, front, and rear).

Figure 2. a) Machine tool configuration for milling tests; b) Illustrative diagram of the front, back and side regions of the chip.

The milling tests were performed dry (without the application of cutting fluid) and with the following fixed cutting parameters: working penetration (a_c) of 5.5 mm and cutting speed (v_c) of 31.41 m/min (spindle rotation $N = 1000$ rpm). Sixteen (16) different cutting conditions were tested by varying two levels of the following four factors: tool edge radius (0.01 and 0.03 mm), depth of cut (1 and 2 mm), feed rate (0.4 and 0.8 mm/rev), and milling mode (down-milling and up-milling). Table 2 shows the experimental design of the milling tests for evaluating the chips generated.

Table 2. Experimental design of milling tests to evaluate chips.

Test Condition	Milling mode	Edge radius (r_{β}) (mm)	Feed rates (f) (mm/rev)	Depth of cut (a_p) (mm)
DM1	Down-milling	0.01	0.4	1
DM2				2
DM3			0.8	1
DM4				2
DM5		0.03	0.4	1
DM6				2
DM7			0.8	1
DM8				2
UM1	Up-milling	0.01	0.4	1
UM2				2
UM3			0.8	1
UM4				2
UM5		0.03	0.4	1
UM6				2
UM7			0.8	1
UM8				2

2.3 Output variables

To analyze the chips generated in the milling tests, the following output variables were evaluated: visual appearance, thickness, microstructure, and microhardness. The qualitative analysis of the chips (visual appearance) was performed by optical microscopy (OM) using an Alltion model D01 900216 stereoscope with a YIZHAN model XHU4003 digital camera attached. Subsequently, chips were cold embedded with self-polymerizing acrylic resin for measuring their thickness (side region as shown in Figure 2b) with the aid of Image J software and the aforementioned OM. Due to their inherent variation, 10 measurements were taken along the side of each chip, and 2 chips were chosen for each condition, totaling 20 measurements in order to obtain representative average values.

For the microstructural analysis, the MTM-1A optical microscope from BEL Photonics with a XHU4003 digital camera from YIZHAN was used to obtain images. The front region of the chips was selected for microstructural analysis and subsequent comparison with the as received (cast) material. Metallographic preparation included sanding with #600, #1200, and #2000 mesh-grade water sandpapers and polishing with 0.05 μm alumina, followed by electrolytic polishing. The sample was then cleaned with cotton moistened with 5% nitric acid solution and subsequently chemically etched with reagents as specified in Table 3.

Table 3. Reagents used for electropolishing and chemical etching.

Type	Reagent	Observation
Electrolytic polishing	40% phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) and 60% ethyl alcohol (99.5%)	SAE 304 stainless steel cathode (10 V/2 min at room temperature)
Chemical Etching	5 g picric acid, 5 ml acetic acid, 1 ml nitric acid, and 100 ml distilled water	Immersion time: 20 s

Vickers microhardness (HV) tests were performed using an INSIZE model ISH-BRV microhardness tester. A total of five indentations were made at the front and rear of the chip for each cutting condition, using a load of 10 gf for 15 seconds. As a reference, the as-cast (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy (as received sample) has an average microhardness of 66.46 ± 4 HV. Sanding and polishing for thickness and Vickers microhardness measurements were performed mechanically on a Fortel PLF model sander/polisher.

For greater reliability of the thickness and microhardness results, their measurements were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a 5% acceptable margin of error, to identify the statistically significant factors in these chip output variables, as well as their main effects and interactions.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Chips morphology

Figure 3 shows the qualitative analysis of the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy chips after down-milling tests (DM1-DM8 as shown in Table 2). One notes that, in general, the use of the smallest depth of cut, $a_p = 1$ mm (conditions DM1, DM3, DM5, and DM7), resulted in comma-shaped chips (indicated by the yellow arrow), while for $a_p = 2$ mm, arc-shaped chips are noted (indicated by the green arrow). In addition, the presence of more fragmented chips (indicated by the red arrows) can be observed in most of the conditions tested.

Figure 4 shows the chips generated after up-milling (UM1-UM8). It can be noticed that most conditions showed more chip fragmentation in comparison to down-milling, especially when using the lowest depth of cut ($a_p = 1$ mm) (conditions UM1, UM3, UM4, UM5, and UM7), making it difficult to clearly distinguish the predominant chip shape (comma or arc). Nevertheless, one notes that considering non-fragmented chips only, chip shape trend maintained the pattern observed in down-milling (Figure 3): comma shape for $a_p = 1$ mm and arc shape for $a_p = 2$ mm.

Figure 3. Stereoscopic of chips under down-milling, with 7x magnification: (a) DM1, (b) DM2, (c) DM3, (d) DM4, (e) DM5, (f) DM6, (g) DM7, and (h) DM8.

In addition, all 16 cutting conditions predominantly produced chips with irregular aspect (similar to burrs), indicated by the blue arrow (Figures 3 and 4), and the rear region of the chips exhibited a more uniform/smooth surface, while the front region had a rougher topography due to the lamellar stacking during chip formation. Based on the analyses performed, it was not possible to identify significant differences in these regions due to the cutting conditions tested in this study.

Thus, in general, the differences in terms of the visual appearance of the chips are small and mainly concentrated in the a_p and milling mode. Comparing conditions with $a_p = 2$ mm (DM2, DM4, DM6, DM8, UM2, UM4, UM6, UM8) and $a_p = 1$ mm (DM1, DM3, DM5, DM7, UM1, UM3, UM5, UM7), illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, it can be observed that $a_p = 1$ mm tends to produce comma-shaped chips, while $a_p = 2$ mm produces arc-shaped chips, which are shorter, but both with the presence of fragmented chips. This difference in shape is in line with the work of Zagórski and Kuczmaszewski[11], who investigated the effects of different cutting parameters on the dry milling of AZ31 and AZ91HP magnesium alloys. The researchers discovered that $a_p > 1.5$ mm with the formation of arc-shaped chips due to increased temperature and friction during cutting.

In addition, Shi et al. [12], when analyzing the morphology of chips generated in the dry machining of the Mg AZ91D alloy, observed that low cutting speeds ($v_c = 50$ m/min) induced chip fragmentation,

and using a fixed a_p of 1.5 mm, generated arc-shaped chips, while higher feed rates ($f = 0.8$ mm/rev) generated chips with more irregular aspects. The authors also attributed these factors to friction and high pressure on the tool during cutting. Thus, these observations help to interpret the current data in this study, in which fragmented chips may be associated with cutting speed ($v_c = 30$ m/min), while arc-shaped chips appear with greater a_p (2 mm), and finally, the predominant presence of irregular aspects in all conditions, caused by the f values used ($f = 0.4$ and 0.8 mm/rev).

Figure 4. Stereoscropy of chips under up-milling, with 7x magnification: (a) UM1, (b) UM2, (c) UM3, (d) UM4, (e) UM5, (f) UM6, (g) UM7, and (h) UM8.

Another aspect evident in Figure 4 is the excessive amount of fragmented chips (UM1, UM3, UM4, UM5, and UM7), which may be associated with the dynamic characteristics of up-milling mode. According to Stephenson and Agapiou[13], for this milling mode, the chip thickness starts close to zero and increases progressively along the edge trajectory, generating an initial condition of low structural support and unstable penetration of the a_p . This condition, combined with the intermittent nature of the process, induces cyclic thermal and mechanical loads that favor chips fragmentation.

Corroborating this statement, Dib et al. [14], in an experimental study with down and up frontal milling, observed that up-milling promotes higher apparent temperature in the cutting zone and more intense shear stresses until the end of the tool trajectory, which can favor chips fragmentation before the end of the effective path of the cutting edge.

In addition, the work of Guo and Salahshoor[15] contributed to understanding the difference between chip surfaces. When studying the surface integrity of the Mg–Ca alloy during dry milling, the authors observed that the front region of the chips, subjected to intense plastic deformation, has high roughness and lamellar structures, while the rear region, in direct contact with the tool, tends to be smoother and more regular, reflecting a more uniform shearing action. Pawanr and Gupta [6] complement this perspective of material plastic deformation by analyzing the chip morphology of the AZ31B Mg alloy and noting that the chips presented irregular and dense shear bands, a characteristic that resembles lamellar structures and is attributed to higher shearing deformation. An example of these regions can

also be seen in Figure 2b. This process highlights the transition of the material from a plastic state to a more brittle state, which can lead to its fragmentation.

Finally, with regard to the qualitative analyses of the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy chips and their cutting conditions studied, the results show that the a_p and milling mode are decisive for chip morphology. $a_p = 2$ mm promoted arc-shaped chips, while $a_p = 1$ mm led to comma-shaped chips, both with the presence of fragmented chips. The up-milling mode amplified the chip fragmentation effect due to the characteristics of initial tool-workpiece engagement, and possible higher thermal loads. Therefore, the combined control of a_p and the milling mode is crucial to predict the geometry and integrity of chips in the machining of Mg alloys.

3.2 Chip thickness analysis

Figure 5 details the average data regarding the thickness of the alloy chips Mg-Zn-RE obtained in the milling tests considering the 16 different cutting conditions tested in this work. The parameters analyzed include the milling mode, whether down-milling (DM) or up-milling (UM), the tool edge radius (0.01 and 0.03 mm), the feed rate (0.4 and 0.8 mm/rev), and the depth of cut (1 and 2 mm). The high standard deviation values are associated with the inherent variation in the uncut chip thickness during milling[13].

Figure 5. Chip thickness results.

The influence of input variables on chip thickness was statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). This type of analysis is useful for identifying which factors (cutting parameters, among others) most affect chip formation, allowing the milling process to be optimized for better results. The factors and interactions that influence the response variable are highlighted in the Pareto chart (Figure 6), allowing them to be ordered from most significant to least significant. The factors considered in the analysis were the edge radius (A), the depth of cut (B), the feed rate (C), and the milling mode (D), as well as the interactions between these parameters.

Figure 6. Pareto chart of standardized thickness effects.

From the Pareto chart shown in Figure 6, it can be noticed that among all factors and interactions, only the edge radius (A) and its interactions with the depth of cut (AB) and feed rate (AC) did not show statistical significance for the response (chip thickness). In addition, the feed rate (C) and milling mode (D) stood out as the factors with the greatest influence on the chip thickness. Figure 7 shows the main effects of each factor.

Regarding the effect of the cutting tool edge radius (Figure 7a), it can be observed that increasing the tool's edge radius from 0.01 mm to 0.03 mm tends to reduce chip thickness. According to Hariprasad et al. [16] and Stephenson and Agapiou[13], a larger edge radius increases the tool-workpiece contact area, which promotes a more uniform distribution of the heat generated by friction during milling. This more balanced heat dissipation can contribute to a reduction in temperature in the cutting region and, consequently, decrease plastic deformation at the tool-workpiece interface, thereby reducing chip thickness.

Figure 7. Main effects plot for thickness.

Regarding depth of cut (a_p), Figure 7b shows that greater a_p contributed to reducing chip thickness. Bolar et al. [17], and Kumar et al. [18], evaluated the thickness of Mg alloy chips (AZ31 and ZM21, respectively) after milling under different cutting conditions and observed that chip thickness increased with a_p . According to the authors, higher values of a_p increase the contact area between the tool and the workpiece, while higher feed rates (f) accelerate the displacement of the tool over the material. This combination of factors reduces the time available for heat dissipation in the workpiece, resulting in a large portion of the thermal energy being transferred to the chips. This heat accumulation promotes plastic deformation of the material, resulting in thicker chips.

In this context, the results observed in this study suggest that the employed a_p had less influence than expected, probably due to the strong influence of the milling mode observed for the conditions tested in this study. When observing Figure 5, and taking into account the standard deviation, it can be noted that, for most conditions, the down-milling mode resulted in greater thickness with lower a_p , while for the up-milling mode, greater thickness was observed when using the higher a_p , which explains the high statistical significance of this interaction (BD) as shown in Figure 6.

Also, in Figure 7c, it can be seen that the increase in feed rate (f) resulted in thicker chips. As already mentioned, feed was the factor that most influenced chip thickness, which was expected, since as the feed value increases, the cutting thickness also grows. This causes an increase in the amount of material removed during the milling process, consequently generating thicker chips [19].

Regarding the milling mode, Figure 7d shows that up-milling resulted in thicker chips, which can be explained by the difference in the material removal mechanism in each case. The up-milling mode starts with a minimum cutting thickness close to zero, and the a_p is forced into the workpiece, creating excessive friction with intense plastic deformation before shearing (chip formation). In addition, contact is made with a hardened surface caused by previous cutting edge. The tool only penetrates the surface and induces plastic deformation of the material when the cutting radius pressure exceeds the shear strength of the workpiece material, leading to material accumulation on the rake face and a gradual increase in chip thickness. Li et al. [20] further report that an initial thickness close to zero can lead to the phenomenon of slippage before the tool penetrates the material. This slippage avoids severe impacts, but also causes complex curvature in the fibers and difficulty in cutting the root of the chips, resulting in burrs on the sides of the machined region.

In the up-milling mode, however, because the initial cutting thickness is maximum when the milling cutter edge comes into contact with the workpiece, the a_p does not come into contact with the layer hardened by the previous cut, and there is no excessive friction from the tool to penetrate the workpiece. In this mode, the cut begins by direct shearing, and the chip thickness tends to decrease progressively along the trajectory of the cutting tool [14].

Figure 8 shows the interaction graphs for the chip thickness results. Among the statistically significant ones, the interaction between f and milling mode (Figure 8f) stands out, in which a sharp increase in chip thickness is obtained with higher f values, especially for up-milling mode. The interaction between a_p and milling mode (Figure 8e), also statistically significant, reveals the behavior already mentioned. For the down-milling mode, increasing the a_p from 1 mm to 2 mm resulted in a reduction in chip thickness, which is in good agreement to the findings of Bolar et al. [17] and Kumar et al. [18]. However, for the up-milling mode, increasing the a_p led to an increase in chip thickness.

Figure 8. Interaction graph for thickness.

3.3 Chips microstructure analysis

Figure 9 shows images of the microstructure of the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy as casting (as-received sample) and after milling under conditions DM1 and UM8. These conditions were chosen as they represent opposite extremes in terms of the input parameters evaluated. As observed in Figure 9a, the as-received sample microstructure consists of an α -Mg (HCP) matrix with Mg-RE (rare earth) intermetallic precipitates, relatively coarse and elongated in morphology, dispersed within the matrix. These characteristics are consistent with the work of Straumal et al. [21], who evaluated the wetting phase of grain boundaries in a cast industrial EZ33A Mg alloy. Even without revealing the grain boundaries, the precipitates are clearly visible and comparable.

Furthermore, in Figure 9a, it can be seen that the absence of well-defined grain boundaries does not prevent the clear identification of intermetallic precipitates distributed throughout the matrix. As discussed by Barros Neto[9], this distribution results from the solidification process, in which the hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure typical of Mg alloys restricts precipitate diffusion and mobility, promoting their retention in specific regions of the matrix. This behavior reinforces the interpretation that the 'ARS' alloy, the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy retains the expected microstructural characteristics of Mg alloys in the as-cast state, in agreement with the observations reported by Straumal et al. [21].

Figure 9. Micrographs of EZ33 alloy samples under the conditions: a) ARS, b) DM1 and c) UM8.

After end milling under conditions DM1 (Figure 9b) and UM8 (Figure 9c), a significant change in the alloy microstructure is observed compared to the as-received sample (Figure 9a). Under condition DM1, the precipitates appear more fragmented and elongated, a behavior also observed after milling under UM8 condition, suggesting a preferential mechanism for accommodating precipitates during the plastic deformation imposed by the milling process. The distribution of precipitates becomes finer and more homogeneous when compared to the ARS sample, with localized deformation features attributable to mechanical stresses generated during cutting. Nevertheless, an intensification of the deformation effects can be noticed for the UM8 condition (Figure 9c), as the precipitates are even more fragmented and with a more evident orientation, thereby suggesting greater severity in plastic deformation during chip formation. The porosities remain visible, but with greater evidence of distortion around them, which reinforces the impact of high plastic deformation when using the up-milling mode.

The increase in the distribution of precipitates after processing by milling was also observed by Wojtowicz et al. [22], who reported a dispersion in microhardness measurements and microstructural changes after machining a (Mg-Zn-RE-Zr) Mg alloy. The authors associate this behavior with the presence of globular Nd precipitates and fine precipitates rich in Zn and Zr, both of which are harder than the matrix (α -Mg). In addition, they also discuss that work hardening modifies the microstructure of Mg during the cutting process due to plastic deformations induced by machining conditions. This suggests that these occurrences may have contributed to the greater quantity and more homogeneous distribution of precipitates in conditions DM1 and UM8. Although the exact identification of the precipitates has not been studied, the combination of work hardening and alloy chemical composition (Table 1) may suggest a significant presence of Nd and Zn in the microstructures of the analyzed conditions.

Pu et al. [23], also analyzed the effects of different machining conditions (dry and cryogenic) on Mg alloy (AZ31B), using tools with edge radius of 0.03 and 0.07 mm, with v_c of 100 m/min and feed rate (f) of 0.1 mm/rev. The authors pointed out that both the machined surface and the chips generated undergo high plastic deformation zones during the machining process, thus generating the formation of a highly refined microstructure in both situations, and on the machined surface, this microstructure is called a “featureless” layer. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was unable to distinguish the grain boundaries in this layer due to its ultra-fine size. However, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), although no measurements of the grains in the chips were made, showed grains with average sizes of 31 nm (nanometers) in the “featureless” layer under severe conditions (e.g., larger edge radius and cryogenic cooling). This suggests an explanation for the absence of grain boundaries in the microstructures (Figure 9b/c) referring to conditions DM1 and UM8.

Finally, comparison of the microstructure of as-received sample with those machined (DM1 and UM8) confirms that the milling process causes a clear predominance of work hardening due to plastic deformation. This effect is reflected in the high density of precipitates and the observed internal deformations, which negate any original influence of the microstructure, suggesting, therefore, an increase in the hardness of the chips generated by the milling process, as well as a possible significant refinement in the microstructure (grain boundaries), although this could not be confirmed through conventional optical microscopy (OM).

3.4 Vickers microhardness (VH) analysis of chips

Figure 10 shows the average Vickers microhardness (HV) values of the chips after the milling process, considering the 16 cutting conditions studied, as well as the hardness of the as-received sample (ARS). It can be observed that the ARS sample had the lowest hardness value (66.46 HV), while the chips generated by milling exhibited higher values, proving a significant increase in chip hardness. Among the cutting conditions evaluated, the highest hardness value (113.73 HV) was observed after milling with UM3 condition (up-milling mode, smaller r_p , $f = 0.8$ mm/rev, and $a_p = 1$ mm), and the lowest value (93.76 HV) for UM5 condition (up-milling mode, larger r_p , $f = 0.4$ mm/rev, and $a_p = 1$ mm).

Thus, considering the conditions tested in this work, the chips generated by the milling process showed an increase in hardness in relation to the workpiece material in the range of 41-71%. This increase is greater than those reported in plastic deformation processes that refine the granular structure in order to improve the mechanical properties of the material, as is the case with the HPT (High Pressure Torsion) process. Bryla et al. [24], for example, observed an increase to 90 HV when using the HPT process with the EZ33 alloy (58 ± 5 HV). These data confirm the effectiveness of milling in increasing the hardness of the generated chips, and being comparable or even more effective in this regard when compared to a severe plastic deformation process.

The increase in microhardness of the chips (Figure 10) compared to the as-received sample is mainly attributed to work hardening caused by plastic deformation during cutting and to the consequent redistribution of precipitates, which are harder than the Mg matrix (as discussed in Section 3.3). Wojtowicz et al. [22], examined the effect of different machining conditions on the hardness of a Mg alloy (Mg-Zn-RE-Zr) and found out values in the range of 70-100 HV, depending on cutting parameters, indentation depth, and microstructural features. These variations were particularly evident in regions affected by plastic deformation and localized work hardening. Comparing the hardness trends of this study with the results of Wojtowicz et al. [21], it is possible to deduce that the deformation mechanisms described by them are active in the chips obtained by milling and investigated in this work.

This behavior further suggests a predominance of work hardening over thermal softening, as highlighted by Marakini et al. [25], who linked hardening to heat transfer at the tool-workpiece interface. In a comparable study on the Mg AZ91 alloy (69.4 HV), they reported increased hardness values when using coated (96.8–111.2 HV) and uncoated (74.4–91.8 HV) milling cutters across 18 machining conditions. However, they also observed a decrease in hardness with increasing cutting speed, which was attributed to excessive heating and thermal softening. Based on these results, the authors emphasized that higher hardness values can be beneficial for enhancing both wear and corrosion resistance of the machined component.

Figure 10. Vickers microhardness (HV) results.

Figure 11 shows the Pareto chart for microhardness results considering the different factors tested in this study, as well as their interactions. It can be observed that factor A (edge radius) had the greatest impact on chips microhardness, followed by its interaction with the milling mode (AD). All other factors were not statistically significant.

Figure 11. Pareto chart of standardized effects for Vickers microhardness (HV).

As can be seen in the main effects plots (Figure 12a), the tool with the smallest edge radius ($r_\beta = 0.01$ mm) tended to generate chips with higher microhardness. According to Kim et al. [25], increasing the tool edge radius widens the plastic deformation region of the metal, advancing deeper into the primary shear zone. Even without significantly altering the chip thickness, the larger radius modifies the stress distribution, distributing them more internally and reducing concentrations due to the larger contact area that widens the shear zone.

According to Póka and Balázs[26], the stresses distribution around the tool edge radius has a direct influence on chip formation because, in situations with thicker chips, the high deformation rate in more external regions causes hardening at the root of the chip (initial thickness). Therefore, even though the edge radius (r_β) did not show statistical significance for thickness (Figure 6), the results of this study show a tendency for smaller r_β (Figure 7a) to generate thicker chips. With unchanged cutting conditions, an increase in chip thickness is directly associated with higher levels of deformation in the initial shear zone. This tends to favor work hardening of the material in cases where the thermal effect is not a major factor (e.g., low cutting speeds), thus resulting in greater microhardness of the chip, as observed in the results of this study.

Figure 12. Main effects plot for Vickers microhardness (HV).

However, the effect observed in relation to the variation in the tool edge radius (Figure 12a) is small, although statistically significant: the increase from 0.01 mm to 0.03 mm in the tool edge radius resulted in an average decrease of 8 HV (from 106 HV to 98 HV), a small variation that does not, in principle, imply differences in the material properties.

The interaction graphs for microhardness results are shown in Figure 13. The interaction between edge radius and milling mode (Figure 13d) is the only statistically significant interaction; as can be noticed, the effect of the tool edge radius was stronger for up-milling mode, although hardness variation is small, reinforcing the general trend of low operational influence. Thus, it can be inferred that, in general, the microhardness of the generated chips showed a statistically higher value than that of the as-received material, and not very sensitive to variations in cutting conditions.

Figure 13. Interaction plot for Vickers microhardness (HV).

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the chips obtained after milling of the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy studied in this work, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- i. Chip thickness analysis showed that f and milling mode directly impact thickness variation, with the highest f (0.8 mm/rev) and up-milling mode, as well as their combinations, being the factors that exert the greatest influence on increasing chip thickness.
- ii. Compared to the as-received material (cast), the chips generated by milling presented higher precipitates' density and plastic deformed microstructure, thereby indicating work hardening occurrence and a consequent increase in chip hardness.
- iii. Microhardness measurements indicated that the edge radius (r_β) parameters and their interaction with the milling mode were statistically significant. Conditions under up-milling mode and smaller r_β resulted in chips with higher microhardness. In addition, all cutting conditions showed a significant increase in chip hardness compared to the as-received material in the range of 41-71%, confirming that the milling process promotes hardening by plastic deformation.
- iv. Qualitative analysis revealed that the milling mode and a_p directly affect chip morphology for the conditions tested in this work. a_p of 1 mm tends to form comma-shaped chips, while arc-shaped chips are observed when using $a_p = 2$ mm. Up-milling promotes greater chip fragmentation compared to concordant milling.
- v. The results of this study reinforce the importance of precise control of cutting parameters to optimize chip formation and improve understanding of the milling of the (Mg-Zn-RE) magnesium alloy, contributing to process improvement and sustainability in the management of machining waste.

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DECLARATIONS

The authors provide the following statements to ensure full transparency, scientific integrity, and reproducibility of the present study:

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no financial, commercial, or personal relationships that could be perceived as influencing the work reported in this study. This statement is made to maintain transparency and uphold the credibility of the research.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated or analyzed during this study are available upon request to the corresponding author. Providing the data is intended to facilitate independent verification of the results and support future research in this area.

DISCLOSURE OF GENERATIVE AI USE

Portions of this manuscript were refined using ChatGPT (GPT-5, OpenAI) to enhance grammar, wording, and overall clarity. The use of this tool was strictly limited to language editing; no content, data analysis, interpretations, or conclusions were generated by AI.

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